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FORMATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation. *The subject of this study is the formation of entrepreneurial competencies of students in pedagogical training areas. Currently, the development of the entrepreneurial culture of society is becoming one of the main tasks of education as a social institution. Its solution lies, first of all, in the formation of entrepreneurial competencies of future teachers, as the central link in the education system.*

Key words: *pedagogical education, development of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial competencies, formation of entrepreneurial competencies, model, organizational and pedagogical conditions, pedagogical process, education sphere, university, youth entrepreneurship*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ

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Аннотация. *Предметом данного исследования является формирование предпринимательских компетенций студентов педагогических направлений подготовки. В настоящее время развитие предпринимательской культуры общества становится одной из основных задач образования как социального института. Ее решение заключается, прежде всего, в формировании предпринимательских компетенций будущих учителей, как центрального звена системы образования.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогическое образование, развитие предпринимательства, предпринимательские компетенции, формирование предпринимательских компетенций, модель, организационно-педагогические условия, педагогический процесс, сфера образования, вуз, молодежное предпринимательство*

Introduction

One of the target guidelines of the modern innovative vector of socio-economic development of Uzbekistan is the activation of entrepreneurship. The development of the entrepreneurial culture of society is becoming one of the main tasks of the state. A special role is given to the education system as the most important factor in the formation of a new quality of the economy and society. According to the majority of scientists, education as a social institution is capable and should ensure an increase in the entrepreneurial activity of citizens.

As noted by R. Ferreira et al., "in a market economy, each citizen and, especially, a specialist with higher education should have developed sustainable competencies in the field of entrepreneurship." To achieve this, it is necessary to create conditions for the effective development of entrepreneurial competencies in the process of obtaining both general and professional education, as well as in the system of additional education, ensuring the implementation of the concept of "lifelong education."

One of the most important areas for successfully solving the identified problems is, first of all, the development of entrepreneurial competencies of teachers, educators, as the central link in the education system. At the same time, the readiness of teachers for entrepreneurial activity as such is not the main goal, since only a small proportion of students in pedagogical fields associate their future with entrepreneurship. At the same time, a modern teacher must have initiative, the ability to make decisions and establish business communications, project and strategic thinking, and professional mobility. Entrepreneurial competencies of teachers should become an important component of their professional competence and ensure effective integration into the innovative educational space both from the point of view of the realization of professional and entrepreneurial potential.

Literature analysis

Today, the study of the problems of developing entrepreneurial education is widely reflected in scientific publications. Innovative approaches and practices for the formation of entrepreneurial competencies of students are presented in the works of Yu. B. Rubin [1], A. Yu. Chepurenko [2], A. V. Lyubanenko [3], A. K. Klyuev [4] and A. A. Yashin, E. B. Goncharova [5] and A. V. Sheina, T. S. Salnikova [6], E. A. Serebrennikova [7], Yu. M. Gavrilenko, A. V. Dudko [8] and others. At the same time, the main vector of research is aimed at the areas of economic and technical education. While the problems of forming entrepreneurial competencies of future teachers currently remain poorly studied. It should be noted that the number of publications on this topic is limited, among which the authors highlight the works of T. A. Voloshina [9], T. A. Potenko, D. V. Mukhina,

and others [10], aimed at updating and developing the theoretical and methodological foundations for the formation of entrepreneurial competencies of students in pedagogical fields. At the same time, the practical aspects of implementing the provisions proposed in the theory remain insufficiently studied; the publications practically lack an analysis of real organizational and pedagogical conditions, experience, and effective practices in teaching entrepreneurship in pedagogical universities.

Analysis and results

In the pedagogical process of forming entrepreneurial competencies of future teachers, the following principles are proposed to be used as fundamental ones: individualization of learning, democratization of learning, student activity, scientific objectivity, professional appropriateness, and integrity of the pedagogical process. At the same time, the possibility of using other well-known pedagogical principles that contribute to the construction of an effective model of this process in specific conditions of place and time is not excluded.

In the structure of entrepreneurial competence as an integral quality of the teacher's personality, the following components can be identified, which form the basis of the substantive block of the model under consideration:

- motivational - is expressed in the formation of value-semantic attitudes, a stable interest in entrepreneurial activity and motives for the formation of entrepreneurial competencies; is implemented through the disclosure of the role and significance of entrepreneurship in the development of innovative educational space, the possibilities and prospects for self-development and self-realization both in professional, pedagogical activity and in the field of educational entrepreneurship;

- cognitive - involves the acquisition by students of a special body of knowledge of the basics of entrepreneurship, including in the field of basic professional education; is successfully implemented using active and interactive forms and methods of teaching (lecture-conversation, problem discussion, business game, joint activities, round table, conference, etc.), facilitating the exchange of knowledge, experience, problems, ways to find their solution, the development of special skills;

- activity-based - involves the development by students of methods of activity characteristic of entrepreneurship, including educational; is implemented by providing the opportunity for practical application of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in real (close to real) conditions of professional and (or) entrepreneurial activity in the process of passing various types of educational and industrial practices, participation in competitions of business projects, grants, etc.;

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- reflexive - expressed in the ability to identify and eliminate existing professional deficiencies, determine one's own educational and professional trajectory.

The formation of entrepreneurial competencies of students as an educational process presupposes the presence of the necessary organizational and pedagogical conditions that determine the possibility of its occurrence, effectiveness and efficiency. In this study, the authors understand organizational and pedagogical conditions as "the characteristics of the pedagogical system, reflecting a set of external and internal capabilities (prerequisites, circumstances, requirements) that ensure goal-setting, the environment of the course, management of development and the effectiveness of the process of forming entrepreneurial competencies of students of pedagogical directions" [10, p. 21].

The study of existing approaches in scientific publications to substantiate the significance of certain conditions for the effectiveness of the formation of entrepreneurial competencies allowed the authors to identify the following organizational and pedagogical conditions as key ones, determining the implementation of the presented model in accordance with the identified blocks and their components:

- definition and consolidation of the formation of entrepreneurial competencies as one of the key tasks of the educational activities of the university, ensuring the achievement of the goal of comprehensive personal development, socialization and self-realization of students of pedagogical directions in modern conditions;

- the presence in the content of the main educational programs of pedagogical areas of training of disciplines/modules, sections of practices, topics of scientific research work, ensuring the formation of the main components of entrepreneurial competencies;

- the presence of additional educational programs, electives, seminars, trainings, master classes on entrepreneurial orientation, providing the opportunity for students to build an individual educational route;

- ensuring the necessary level of qualification, economic and entrepreneurial competence of the teaching staff, entrepreneurs-practitioners, employees of educational organizations participating in the implementation of basic and additional educational programs;

- ensuring and supporting the participation of students in business project competitions in the field of education and grant competitions for their implementation.

The degree of development of the listed conditions allows us to determine the level of integration of the model for developing entrepreneurial competencies

into the educational process of a particular university. In this case, we believe it is appropriate to distinguish the following three levels:

- the highest - the development of the entrepreneurial culture of society is embedded in the mission of the pedagogical university; the target settings of educational activities are aimed at developing entrepreneurial competencies as an important component of the professional training of a teacher; organizational and pedagogical conditions fully ensure the possibility and necessary level of developing entrepreneurial competencies of students;

- average - one of the tasks of the educational process in pedagogical areas of training is the development of general economic literacy of students; the development of entrepreneurial competencies is considered as one of the possible educational trajectories; students are given the opportunity to study the basics of entrepreneurship within the framework of electives, additional education programs, seminars, trainings and other entrepreneurial events; organizational and pedagogical conditions provide, at best, the opportunity to obtain basic knowledge and skills in the field of entrepreneurship;

- lowest - there are no target settings for the formation of economic literacy and entrepreneurial culture of students; the combination and degree of development of organizational and pedagogical conditions do not provide the possibility of forming even the minimum threshold level of entrepreneurial competencies.

The analysis of the practice of teaching entrepreneurship in the system of modern pedagogical education, presented in publications, indicates a significant differentiation in the level of integration of the model of forming entrepreneurial competencies in the educational process of individual educational organizations. In our opinion, this is largely due to the different attitudes of the management of pedagogical universities to entrepreneurship, the degree of awareness of its strategic role in the formation of an innovative economy and the development of human capital of society.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the formation of an innovative economy and the need to develop entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan require both the Russian pedagogical education system as a whole and directly from the management of pedagogical universities to take practical steps to create and develop conditions for the effective implementation of the model for the formation of entrepreneurial competencies of students. Everything must be done so that entrepreneurial initiative is reflected in young people, especially those who have received higher education.

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